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Research Article

“G-D’s Physics: The Origin of All Origins!”

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Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm based on a “time-sensitive” measurement of a predicted increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days’ time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish’s e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a Paradigmatic-Shift from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory”, CUFT) following a fundamental “Paradigmatic-Crisis” appearing in the Old Paradigm (e.g., signified by an apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and a principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe); Significantly, this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving this GRT-QM inconsistency and offered a (satisfactory) alternative theoretical account for this accelerated expansion of the universe based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for each consecutive “Universal Frame/s” (UF’s) at an incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ” (!) Nevertheless, for this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm to be accepted (unequivocally) by the Scientific Community, it also has to satisfy a key (stringent) criteria pointed at by Thomas Kuhn involving the identification of at least one unique “Critical Prediction” differentiating this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (of GRT & QM)! Indeed, based on the empirical validation of two such unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” as more valid than the predictions of GRT & QM – “G-D’s Physics” is unequivocally accepted as the New Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First century! Based on its “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, “G-D’s Physics” is shown to negate some of the basic “material-causal” assumptions of the Old Paradigm, including: the “Big-Bang” Model, the existence of “dark-matter” (as “superfluous”, i.e., “non-existent”!); instead pointing at the “Origin of all origins”: this singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” which has “pre-planned” the whole development of the entire physical universe – from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State”, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR also being characterized by its profound characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

Introduction

Twenty-first century Theoretical Physics has undergone a fundamental “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying Twentieth century’s General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory”, CUFT)! This Paradigmatic-Shift (inevitably) ensued following the existence of a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm signified by the appearance of a basic “theoretical inconsistency” between its two (above) “pillars”, e.g., GRT & QM, and its principle inability to account for the empirically observed accelerated expansion of the physical universe – i.e., assumed to be “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but yet failed to be verified experimentally despite intensive experimentation trying to do so over the past two full decades?! Indeed, according to Thomas Kuhn’s well known (and broadly accepted) description of the “[1-51], whenever there appears such a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” what follows is the discovery of a New Scientific Paradigm which is capable of resolving this apparent “theoretical inconsistency” (between GRT & QM), ability to replicate all of the previously known data and phenomena, offering of an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical account for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – and most importantly: identi-

fication of at least one (or more) unique “Critical Predictions” which can differentiate this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, which if validated empirically (e.g., as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm’s GRT’s & QM’s; then this, would (unequivocally) “crown” the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Paradigm as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Succinctly stated, the manner in which this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm is able to resolve the apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between GRT & QM is based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) which is postulated to simultaneously compute all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., including their four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time” – at an unfathomably rapid rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ (sec)}^{-1}$ ” (!) This produces an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at every such “minimal time point”, e.g., with all such exhaustive spatial pixels “dissolving” back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frames! Additionally, as part of the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the en-

tire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s, it also computes "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) relativistic "object" or subatomic "particle" computation, as well as "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) computation of more than one spatial-temporal "object"/"particle" point at any given UF's frame/s, e.g., giving rise to the (relativistic or subatomic) "wave" phenomenon! Thus, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's theoretical framework is capable of explicating the embedding of any SSP "particle", e.g., including two "entangled particles" as integral parts of the broader "MST" "wave" phenomenon – which are both embedded within the "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) UCP's computation of the entire UF's frame/s (e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame)! Viewed from this novel higher-ordered perspective of the UCP's EST computation of all exhaustive spatial temporal pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as embedding within it both the SST "entangled particles" and the broader MST "wave" computation allows for this New "G-D's Physics" to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM – while pointing at the much more exhaustive theoretical framework of the UCP's production of the series of UF's frame/s!

Indeed, a major discovery made by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the complete unification – not only between GRT & QM, but also between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as well as between the four basic Forces!) within a newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which explicates the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This major UCF discovery stems from "G-D's Physics" novel computation of these four basic physical features as underlie by the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency": According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm the UCP computes for each given (relativistic or subatomic) object – its degree of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") relative to two possible "Framework" levels, i.e., relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "object" itself (i.e., internal composition), which gives rise to those four basic physical features; That is, when the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" measures of any given object this yields the two corresponding physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas when the UCP computes the two "Object" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" measures this produces the two corresponding physical features of "mass" and "time"! Based on these new (and exciting) UCP's computational definitions of these four basic physical features (given below) the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was able to integrate them as secondary computational features of the same singular higher-ordered UCP, thereby giving rise to this profound novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)!

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF):

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} \text{UF's } \{n \dots n \dots n\} [Px]_{\{a \dots z\}} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

$$S: (f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] + \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n) \leq f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] - \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n) > f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i \dots n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i \dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i \dots n) \leq c * h \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ($E = Mc^2$) and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM! However, since one of the key Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels – "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm has been characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and its complete "dissolution" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames (e.g., back into the UCP's singular existence), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In fact, due to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., which exists only "during" the UCP's production of every consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frames, two additional profound Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm, termed: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate: a) That the only "computationally-invariant" principle in the universe which exists both "during" the UCP's successive computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s, and solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP); as opposed to the only "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the entire physical universe – regarded as "computationally-variant", e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed or produced by this singular UCP) but "dissolving" back into the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; b) Therefore, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly – both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and also exists singularly "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)!

Viewed from this new (higher, more exhaustive) perspective of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a series of additional (profound) associated Theoretical Postulates have been discovered, including: a) The "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: hypothesizing that since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, the only manner in which this series of UF's frames (comprising the entire physical universe) could "evolve" is based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's "pre-planning" of the entire evolution- (or manifestation-) of the whole universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": "plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards", i.e., based on the UCP's "pre-planning" of the whole evolution of all "inanimate" and "animate" forms leading up to this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! A Metaphor regarding "King Solomon's"

build-up of the Divine Temple was utilized to explain this "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: that is, in the same way that King Solomon must have received a completed "Perfected Blue-Print Plan" of the "Ultimate Completed Temple State" (e.g., and all of the necessary "steps" required to reach this "Ultimate Completed Temple State" – prior to his various builders starting to construct this immaculate Divine Temple, so it is postulated that the UCP/UCR must have "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter", "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" – through the entire evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, ultimately leading to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", i.e., in which Science and the whole of Humanity will recognize the singular existence of this higher-ordered UCR, alongside the recognition of its basic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (previously delineated).

A Brief Summary of "G-D's Physics" additional Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

b) The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

c) The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of

"All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole-source of the Universal Consciousness Reality! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת)

signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Teshuva"/חשבה):

this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Gevorah"/גבורה):

denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human

beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

the sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת"/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification-

or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נצח"/"Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"("תשובה")/דוה"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יִסוּד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal

time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"תוכלמ"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising

any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "דוסי"/"Yessod"-"Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר"/"Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "רתכ"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

FIGURE 2. The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

One of the clear theoretical distinctions between the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm and the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm has to do with their diametrically opposed theoretical conceptions of the "origin" of the universe – and likewise, the "evolution" and also (stipulated) "end-state" of the physical universe! According to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT & QM) every phenomena in the physical universe – including its hypothesized initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event occurs merely based on ("random": direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain material or physical elements, forces (e.g., such as GRT's assumed direct "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive objects" and their assumed "causing" of the "curvature of 'Space-Time' etc.) or between certain physical properties of given subatomic particles (e.g., such as the direct physical interaction/s between a given subatomic "probe" particle and its corresponding assumed "target's probability wave function" – which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of this "probability wave function" into a singular "complimentary": "space-energy", or "mass-time" value); In contrast, according to the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT), any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction is strictly negated – based on its basic discovery of the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., for every consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of this UCP! Therefore, according to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, thereby negating the very basic assumption underlying the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of GRT & QM)!

Ensuing from this profound discovery of this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is its negation of some of the most fundamental tenets of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm: a) Negation of the "Big-Bang" Model associated with GRT! Based on the above-mentioned "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's insistence upon the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), the basic assumption wherein the physical universe was created by an initial "Big-Bang" initial nuclear event is strictly negated: since the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe), there could not have been any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any such stipulated initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the creation of all the suns, galaxies, matter, energy space or time (e.g., assumed to have happened as "caused" by this initially assumed nuclear event)?! This is simply because at none of the UF's – the "first", "second"... Trillionth... Nth UF's frame/s from the beginning of this stipulated "Big-Bang" nuclear event (e.g., and until the "present" UF's frame/s) can there exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all such exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! Moreover, since all of these exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP ("in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s), therefore there cannot also exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels that exist in any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

So, we find that according to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm the universe could not have been created (or "caused") by any such (initial) "Big-Bang" nuclear event! Likewise, GRT's conception of the continuous accelerated expansion of the universe – as "caused" by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter", (e.g., assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be detected despite two full decades of intensive experimentations trying to do so?!); is also strictly negated

by the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm! This is because, once again, even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" could exist (somehow), its assumed direct "material-causal" physical interaction/s with certain galactic elements in the universe, i.e., "causing" them to "expulse" from each other, thereby creating the accelerated expansion of the universe – is negated by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal" Computation Paradigm, which asserts that there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frames (as noted above)! In any event, the key point to be noted, is that in order for Science to accept the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, it is necessary to contrast at least one of its unique "Critical Prediction/s" with the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT & QM: to the extent that even one such (unique) "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" is validated empirically as more valid than the corresponding prediction of GRT & QM, then this will unequivocally lead to the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Method & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x, o-y, o-z\}) \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x, o-y, o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: \{O_i\{x, y, z\} UF's(i) - O_n\{x, y, z\} UF's(i \dots n)\} \leq n * h \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [51,55].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction [51,55], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x, o-y, o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [50], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, [54,58], higher dimension gravity, [49], a new boson, (McKeen & Miller, 2016) and the quasi-free hypothesis π^+ [52], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashanah" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"

and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Hence, to the extent that these two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm are empirically validated, then this will convince the Scientific Community that the New "G-D's Physics" has to be accepted as a satisfactory New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics! Based on such direct empirical validation of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a discussion ensues of the manner in which "G-D's Physics" newly discovered singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) is capable of computing every exhaustive spatial pixel or "object" (e.g., including "human-beings" as opposed to "non-human": "inanimate" material object/s, as well as "animate": plants and animals) – based on a further discovery of the UCP's "Gimateria" (i.e., Hebrew letters' numerical values) of each object's five "secondary-essential" "Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (HCD's) of: "Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod" (e.g., each of them comprising "ten zero's" out of the "fifty zero's" comprising the incredible rate of the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe: $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec^c)! As will be discussed, this entirely new conception of the manner in which this singular, higher-ordered UCP computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's "object" in the universe is "non-material", i.e., exemplifying the "translation" of the fundamental new "building-blocks" ("or "Atoms" – metaphorically) of the entire physical universe from the Hebrew letters' "Gimatria" (numerical values, also associated with these five "secondary-essential" HCD's corresponding "ten zero's") to the production of each ("human" or "non-human") object's unique physical characteristics! Indeed, it is shown that this novel manner in which the UCP is seen to compute the specific physical characteristics of each individual (unique "human" or "non-human") "object" is a part and parcel of the UCP's overall "Blueprint Plan" of steering the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" material composition through its "animate": "plants", "animals", human-beings – leading to the fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of a "Moral", "Spiritual" and even "Physical" "Perfected" state of the universe in which the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), e.g., characterized by "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" being recognized (and accepted) by Science and Humanity (more generally)!

Discussion

Based upon these results findings, indicating that there exist (in fact) two (unique) “Critical Predictions” that differentiate the New “G-D’s Physics” – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” predictions substantiate “G-D’s Physics” as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First century Theoretical Physics!

Several key (profound) theoretical implications ensue from this “dramatic” acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” as more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM):

a) Since “G-D’s Physics” represents an “A-Causal Computation” New Scientific Paradigm, i.e., which posits that it is the existence (and operation) of a singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s, thereby creating the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF’s frame – at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$!”); then this New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., existing either in the “same” or “different” UF’s frame/s, as shown previously)! This is simply because if this UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s), therefore there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) physical interaction/s between any two (or more) such consecutive spatial pixels within any (single) UF’s frame! And since the entire physical universe “dissolves” “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s back into the singularity of this UC, therefore there cannot also exist any “material-causal” interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing at different UF’s frame/s!

This implies that the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm challenges (and in fact negates) the “Big-Bang” Model’s assumption wherein the entire physical universe was created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event, which created all of the suns, galaxies, planets, “energy”, “space”, “mass” and “time” etc.!? This is because if this singular (higher-ordered) UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF’s frame/s), then this implies that even for the “first”, “second”, “third”... “trillionth”... UF’s frame/s there could not have been any “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – i.e., including between this (assumed) initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event and the creation of all the suns, galaxies, planets, “energy”, “mass” “space” and “time” etc.

b) The Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s assumption regarding the (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” as “causing” the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion – is also strictly negated by the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm! Over and beyond the “disturbing” fact that despite two decades of intensive attempts to detect the presence of this “elusive” “dark-matter” (purely hypothetical) element, no direct empirical evidence exists for the actual existence of “dark-matter”?! Even theoretically, due to “G-D’s Physics” empirically validated New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm’s insistence upon the simultaneity of the UCP’s computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF’s frame/s) – then this principally negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in any single- or multiple- UF’s frame/s!), e.g., including between any such (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” and any possible “galactic-elements” which may “causes” this accelerated expansion of the universe! At a deeper “theoretical-computational” level, it’s been shown that one of the key Theoretical Postulates of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm called the “Computational Duality Principle”

(CDP) also strictly negates the Old “Material-Causal” basic assumption underlying GRT’s assumption regarding the accelerated expansion of the universe as being underlie by this (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter”:

c) “G-D’s Physics” Negates the Second Law of Thermodynamics! Another profound implication of the New (empirically validated) “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm is its (principle) negation of the “Second Law of Thermodynamics” stipulating that there is a given “causal relationship” between the passage of “time” – and an inevitable “increase in the Entropic level” of any given Physical System, e.g., including the entire physical universe! But, since (as we’ve already seen), “G-D’s Physics” New (validated) “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing at any single or multiple UF’s frame/s), e.g., due to the simultaneity of the UCP’s computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single or multiple UF’s frame/s (and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s); therefore, there cannot also exist any such “material-causal” physical relationship/s between the passage of “time” – as “causing” an “increase in the Entropic level” of any given Physical System, i.e., including the assumed “dissolution” of all “suns”, “galaxies”, and “life” as a result of this “Second Law of Thermodynamics” assumed increase in the “Entropic level” of all components in the universe!

d) “G-D’s Physics” “Computational Invariance”, “Universal Consciousness Reality” & “Reversed Time Geulah Goal Postulates! The alternative offered by “G-D’s Physics” as an explanation for the “origin”, “sustenance” and indeed “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of the entire physical universe stems from its “Computational Invariance Principle”, “Universal Consciousness Reality” and “Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hypothesis” Theoretical Postulates! As noted (above and previously), according to the “Computational Invariance Principle” and associated “Universal Consciousness Reality” postulates: since only this “computationally-invariant” “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” exists both “during” its computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s (including every exhaustive spatial pixel’s four basic physical features), as well as solely exists “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s (without the presence of any physical universe), whereas the entire physical universe is regarded only as a “computationally-variant” “transient-phenomenal” manifestation of this singular UCP, e.g., existing only “during” each consecutive UF’s (as solely computed by this singular UCP), but “dissolves back” into the singularity of this UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s; therefore, only this singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Principle/Reality” (UCP/UCR) may be regarded as “continuous”, “permanent” and “constant” (existing both “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s and also “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s), whereas the four basic physical features of the universe (e.g., and in fact the whole existence of the physical universe) is seen only as a “transient-phenomenal manifestation” of this singular “Universal Consciousness Reality”! Indeed, once we realize that that the existence of the entire physical universe is only a “transient-phenomenal manifestation” of this singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical relationships between any (one) UF’s frame/s and any subsequent UF’s frame/s (e.g., or between any single or multiple exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single or multiple UF’s frame/s); then this led to the discovery of the “Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hypothesis” indicating that the entire creation- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe has to be “pre-planned” by this singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Principle/Reality” (UCP/UCR) from the (end) “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” state of the universe in which the whole of Humanity (and Science) recognizes the singularity of this UCP/UCR – “backwards” to the whole “pre-planned” succession of development of

the universe, i.e., from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings (leading up to this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal”)! A Metaphor of King Solomon’s construction of the Immaculate Temple was previously illustrated – pointing out that for King Solomon to summon the various builders of this “Immaculate Temple”, it was necessary for him to possess a complete “Blueprint Plan” for all of the (intricate) architectural “phases” necessary to construct this completed Immaculate Temple (beforehand)! In the same manner, the “Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hypothesis” posits that in order for the UCP/UCR to create- sustain- and develop- the entire physical universe (e.g., as well as every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) has to similarly be “pre-planned” by this singular UCP/UCR, i.e., as leading from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings – to this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal”, in which the whole of Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR, as well as its profound characteristics (of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” characterizing Humanity’s and the universe’s “Perfected Geulah Goal” State)!

e) “G-D’s Physics” Negates Darwin’s “Natural Selection Principle” Evolutionary Theory! As delineated (previously) “G-D’s Physics” New (empirically validated) “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm also principally negates Darwin’s “Natural Selection Principle” Evolutionary Theory, i.e., due to the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s), and the complete “dissolution” of all such exhaustive spatial pixels “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s back into the singularity of the UCP! This is because the basic “Material-Causal” assumption of “Darwin’s Natural Selection Principle” (DNSP) is that the evolution of the various Biological Species stems from two closely related “material-causal” processes, namely: a) “Random” occurrence of certain “genetic mutation/s” which produce a “more compatible organism”; and b) “Adverse Environmental Conditions” that “prefer” those “more compatible organism/s” over other “non-mutated” organism/s that therefore cannot “survive” within this “altered” “Adverse Environmental Conditions”; But, since both of these “material-interaction” based (assumed) processes are strictly negated through “G-D’s Physics” (empirically proven) “A-Causal Computation” due to the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s, and the complete “dissolution” of all such exhaustive spatial pixels “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s) therefore there could not have existed any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s – either between any (a) “cosmic rays” and their assumed “causing” of any “genetic-mutations” in any “more compatible organism/s”, nor between (b) any (altered) “Adverse Environmental Conditions” and any (assumed) “more compatible organism/s”; i.e., at any single or multiple UF’s frames!

f) “G-D’s Physics” Complete Integration of GRT & QM, the Four Physical Features, Four Forces & All Physical, Biological, Moral & Spiritual Developments in the Universe!

Instead, the great “beauty and elegance” of this New (empirically proven) “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm is that it completely integrates not only between GRT & QM, the four basic physical features (and the Four Forces, all shown previously!); but also completely integrates between all Physical, Biological, Moral and Spiritual aspects of development of the universe! As outlined previously, “G-D’s Physics” newly discovered “Universal Computational Formula” (UCF) completely integrates (for the first time in Physics) between the four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”, as well as between GRT & QM (and also the Four basic Forces of Nature)! But the profound implication of this article is that based on the empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm it is also points at the singular higher-ordered “Origin of all origins”, i.e., due to “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm which negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any (two or

more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any (single or multiple) UF’s frame/s, therefore the singular UCP/UCR is recognized not only as the “Origin” of the physical universe – as solely computing (simultaneously) all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, for each consecutive UF’s frame/s); but also as the sole “Universal Consciousness Reality” that manifests as this physical universe “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s (but remains without any physical universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s) that has “pre-planned” the whole development of the entire physical universe – i.e., from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings and up to its “Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State” (Physically, Morally and Spiritually)!

Dedication

This article is dedicated to my Beloved (diseased) mother, Dr. Tirzah Bentwich (whose encouragement has allowed me to pursuit and discover this profound New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm!) It is dedicated to the great Lubavitcher Rabbi whose Vision steers the whole of Humanity and the World towards this Ultimate Perfected Geulah State, and to the “Great Eagle”, Maimonides! Who in his Great Wisdom pointed at the existence of the “Pillar of all Pillars” – this Singular Higher “G-D” Reality (by which all other elements and beings exist!) It is also dedicated to my Beloved wife, Shulamit Bentovish (without whom these articles could not have been possible!)

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